

Comparisons of Safety and Efficacy of Oral Bilastine with Fluticasone Nasal Spray in Patients with Allergic Rhinitis Treated in a Tertiary Care Centre, Bangalore

Shilpa R¹, Shruthi HS², Adarsh AS³, Lohit K⁴

¹Assistant Professor of ENT, Department of ENT, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123

²Associate Professor of ENT, Department of ENT, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123

³Assistant Professor of ENT, Department of ENT, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123

⁴Professor and HOD of Pharmacology, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shilpa R

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Intranasal corticosteroids and oral antihistamines are both effective in the treatment of seasonal allergic rhinitis. Reports between intranasal steroid fluticasone furoate as a first line therapy and newer second generation oral antihistamine Bilastine rarely exists.

Aim of the Study: To compare the efficacy and safety of fluticasone furoate nasal spray (FF NS) and oral Bilastine in the treatment of seasonal allergic rhinitis.

Materials: A retrospective study was conducted on 45 patients diagnosed and treated for Allergic Rhinitis with fluticasone furoate nasal spray (FF NS) and oral Bilastine for one month. Total patients were divided as two groups; Group A only fluticasone furoate nasal spray (FF NS) was used and in Group B patients only oral Bilastine was used. Demographic data and nasal symptom scores were recorded and analysed for their efficacy.

Results: Total nasal symptom scores were significantly lower ($P < .001$) in the group A (FF INS) than in the group B (oral Bilastine) for blockage, discharge, itching, and sneezing.

Conclusions: In the treatment of seasonal allergic rhinitis, FF NS 110 µg once daily was superior, well tolerated and more effective to Bilastine.

Keywords: Fluticasone Furoate, Bilastine, Allergic Rhinitis.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Allergic rhinitis is a type of inflammation in the nose that occurs when the immune system overreacts to allergens in the air. The underlying mechanism involves IgE antibodies that attach to an allergen, and subsequently result in the release of inflammatory chemicals such as histamine from mast cells. [1-4] It is usually long standing condition that often goes undetected especially in the primary-care setting. Causal agents include molds, pollen, dust mites, and animal dander that deposit on the mucosal membrane of the nose and trigger the allergic rhinitis response. The prevalence of allergic diseases, including asthma, rhinitis, anaphylaxis, or food, drug, or insect allergy, is rising worldwide. Over 400 million people suffer from allergic rhinitis around the world [2]. The reported incidence of allergic rhinitis in the western countries is 1.4%-39.7% while in India ranges be-

tween 20% and 30% [1-4] Seasonal rhinitis is more prevalent among children, while adults are more affected by perennial rhinitis. [4] Clinically, allergic rhinitis is characterized by four key symptoms, namely, clear rhinorrhea, sneezing, nasal itch, and nasal congestion. These symptoms disrupt sleep, cause fatigue and depression, compromise cognitive function, and lower quality of life (QoL), all of which affect performance at work and productivity [5]. Allergic Rhinitis patients have often comorbidity with diseases such as Asthma, nasal polypsis, chronic hyperplastic eosinophilic sinusitis, and serous otitis media. The treatment goal for allergic rhinitis targets underlying inflammation and its systemic manifestations with relief of symptoms. Therapeutic options available to achieve this goal include immunotherapy, medications and allergen avoidance. Among medications, the

second generation oral anti-histamines loratadine, cetirizine, fexofenadine have been routinely used by primary care physicians and ENT surgeons. Recently two new second generation anti-histamines Bilastine and Rupatadine are available in the market. Other modalities like intranasal corticosteroids, oral decongestants, intranasal cromolyn, intranasal anticholinergics, and leukotriene receptor antagonists also form part of treatment for allergic rhinitis. [9] There are very few studies available on intra-nasal steroid fluticasone furoate molecule unlike fluticasone propionate as treatment option for allergic rhinitis. Abundant research on routinely prescribed anti-histamines cetirizine, loratadine, and fexofenadine and leukotriene receptor antagonist montelukast has been done alone or in combination with intranasal steroid fluticasone propionate but no comparative reports between intranasal steroid fluticasone furoate as a first line therapy and newer second generation oral anti-histamine Bilastine exists. This study results may recommend better management of patients in future and improved quality of life accordingly. In the current study, various rhinitis parameters will be reviewed from records of patients diagnosed with allergic rhinitis and who had been treated with oral bilastine or intra nasal fluticasone furoate spray for one month.

Type of Study: Retrospective analytical study

Period of Study: Study during the period of May 2023 to May 2024.

Institute of Study: Department of ENT, SSIMS & RC, T BEGUR, Bangalore Rural.

Material and Methods

This Retrospective study was carried out in the department of ENT, SSIMS & RC, T BEGUR, Bangalore Rural. Data was retrieved from hospital records.

Inclusion Criteria: All allergic rhinitis patients of either gender between 20 to 60 years were included. Patients with symptoms of nasal blockage, runny nose, nasal itching, sneezing, eye tearing, redness, itching and difficulty in sleep were included. Patients treated with intra nasal fluticasone furoate spray at a dose of 110 mcg once daily (group A) or oral bilastine 20mg once daily for one month duration (group B) were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with Non-Allergic Rhinitis, Nasal blockage due to DNS or any other structural abnormality, Nasal Polyps, Hypertension, Diabetes, Immuno-compromised status or use of steroids for any other condition. Patients with Allergic Rhinitis and history of addiction such as smoking, alcohol, tobacco or using steroids at the time of study were excluded. An Institution ethics committee approval was obtained and ethics committee approved proforma and consent form

was used for the study. Demographic data was obtained such as age, gender, onset of allergy and social status. A detailed history of allergy and details pertaining to personal and medical history, Total Nasal and Ocular Symptom Score (TSS) were noted. Efficacy of the treatment therapy was documented based on surveillance from record of patients who had visited after one month of completion of treatment by analyzing the changes in TSS mentioned in the records. Those patients who were lost to follow up were excluded. After exclusion, final sample size retrieved was 40 out of which 20 patients were treated with intranasal fluticasone furoate spray at a dose of 110 mcg once daily (group A) and another 20 patients were prescribed oral bilastine 20mg once daily for one month duration at our hospital.

Efficacy Analysis:

Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential tests were used to compare the outcomes between the two groups. Total symptom score (TSS) was calculated as the sum of scores for 4 nasal symptoms (rhinorrhea, congestion, itching and sneezing) and 3 ocular symptoms (tearing, redness, and itching) each symptom was assessed on a 4-point scale: 0- none (no signs/ symptoms), 1- mild (symptom clearly present but easily tolerated), 2- moderate (symptom bothersome but tolerable), 3- severe (symptom difficult to tolerate- interferes with activities). The maximum score for TSS was calculated 15 for each documented point. The change in Nasal symptom score (NSS) & non-nasal symptom scores (NNSS) from baseline to 10 days was assessed as primary endpoint. Secondary endpoints included changes in NSS, NNSS and TSS at 30th day was noted.

Statistical Analysis: The statistical data was analyzed with SPSS (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA) version 23.0 for Windows. The categorical and continuous variables was represented as frequency (percentage) and mean (standard deviation, SD), respectively. The changes in TNSS, TOSS, TSS scores were estimated using repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by post-hoc analyses with Bonferroni multiple comparison test. The association between categorical and continuous variables was assessed with Chi-square and independent sample t-test, respectively. A two-tailed probability value of < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

Data on 45 patients diagnosed and treated for Allergic Rhinitis during the period May 2023 to May 2024 was collected from our hospital records.

Patient demographics and baseline characteristics: Of 45 patients data collected from records, all 45 satisfied the eligibility criteria and

were enrolled in the study. Out of 45 enrolled patients, 5 patients were excluded from the study as their data was missing on one month follow up

report. Mean (SD) age of patients was 34.07 (10.06) years.

Figure 1: Patient disposition

Table 1: Patient Demographics

Data	FF NS	Bilastine
Number of patients	n=20	n=20
Age (Years)	20 to 60	20 to 60
Mean (SD)	34.07 (10.06)	34.07 (10.06)
Sex, no. (%)		
Females	14 (35)	14 (35)
Males	09 (23)	08 (20)
Compliance (%)	97.9	96.8
Patients withdrawn, no (%)		
Adverse Events	NIL	NIL
Failed to return	03 (06.6)	02 (04.4)
Lack of Efficacy	NIL	NIL
Other	NIL	NIL

Efficacy Data: Patients had recorded their nasal and ocular symptoms and use of study medication daily on diary cards throughout the treatment phase. Nasal and ocular symptoms were assessed by the clinician on day 0 (before the first dose of drug was administered), day 10- primary end point, and day 30- secondary end point. During the treatment period, patients were not permitted to use any other medication that might affect rhinitis symptoms. At every clinic visit, clinicians had recorded the occurrence of adverse events (defined as any untoward medical occurrence, drug-related or not), also had recorded concomitant medications used and had checked compliance by diary card and capsule counts, and had examined patients for evidence of nasal and oropharyngeal Candidiasis.

At baseline, total nasal symptom scores were significantly different between treatment groups. At hospital visit, After 1 month of therapy, total nasal symptom scores were significantly lower (p vale at < .001) in the group A (FF INS) than in the group B (oral Bilastine) for blockage, discharge, itching, and sneezing.

Change in TSS in Group A patients (n-20): Efficacy of once daily Fluticasone furoate intra nasal spray in Group A patients following 04 weeks of treatment in terms of Change in TSS: The mean (SD) TSS decreased from 13.7 (±2.35) at baseline to 06.4 (±0.55) at day 10 and to 04.5 (±0.75) at day 30. At both post-baseline visits, there was statistically significant decrease in mean TSS (p<0.0001; Table 2 & Figure 2)

Table 2: Change in TSS for allergic rhinitis at 0 Day, Day 10 and Day 30 (n-20) from baseline to day 30 (n-40)

Nasal Symptom score	Base line – 0 Day	Primary end point 10 th day	Secondary end point 30 th day
Total Symptom Score TSS	13.7±2.35	06.44±0.55	04.5±0.75

Figure 2: Showing Bar Graph of Total Symptom Score of NSS in the study (n-40)

Change in NSS and NNSS in Group A patients (n-20): The mean (SD) NSS decreased from 09.2 (±2.15) at baseline to 05.5 (±1.05) at day 10 and 02.2 (±0.45) at day 30. At both post-baseline visits, a statistically significant decline in NSS was observed (p<0.0001; (Table 3 & Figure 3A). Mean

(SD) NNSS decreased from 03 (±0.15) at baseline to 02.2 (±0.85) at day 10 and then marginally to 01.2 (±0.35) at day 30. At both visits, there was statistically significant decrease in NNSS from baseline (p<0.0001; Figure 3B).

Figure 3 (A and B): Change in NSS and NNSS for allergic rhinitis from baseline to day 30 in Bar Graph (n-40)

Change in TSS in Group B patients (n-20):

Efficacy of once daily bilastine following 04 weeks of treatment; Change in TSS, Mean (SD) TSS decreased from 10.7 (± 2.66) at baseline to 07 (± 3.88) at day 10 and to 05.3 (± 1.40) at day 30. Thus, mean (SD) change in TSS from baseline -3.7

(4.16) and -5.4 (5.83) at days 10 and 30, respectively.

At both post-baseline visits, there was statistically significant decrease in mean TSS ($p < 0.0001$; Figure 4)

Figure 4: Change in TSS for allergic rhinitis from baseline to day 30 in Group B patients in Bar Graph

Change in NSS and NNSS in Group B patients (n-20):

The mean (SD) NSS decreased from 07.2 (± 2.67) at baseline to 04.5 (± 2.82) at day 10 and 03.2 (± 2.01) at day 30. Thus, mean (SD) change in NSS from baseline was -2.7 (3.72) and -4.1 (4.36) at days 10 and 30, respectively. At the both post-baseline visits, a statistically significant decline in NSS was observed ($p < 0.0001$; (Figure 5A). The

mean (SD) NNSS decreased from 03.5 (± 1.60) at baseline to 02.5 (± 1.85) at day 10 and then marginally to 02.2 (± 2.22) at day 30. Thus, mean (SD) change in NNSS from baseline was -0.99 (1.33) and -1.3 (1.91) at days 10 and 30, respectively. At the both visits, there was statistically significant decrease in NNSS from baseline ($p < 0.0001$; Figure 5B).

Figure (5A and 5B): Change in NSS and NNSS for allergic rhinitis from baseline to day 30

Safety Data: The incidence and pattern of drug-related adverse events did not differ among the treatment groups. In both group A and B; no Adverse Effects were reported during the study.

Discussion

In this study in Indian patients with allergic rhinitis, significant decrease in allergic rhinitis symptoms was noted after the treatment with intranasal fluticasone furoate spray at a dose of 110 mcg once daily given for 1 month duration than in the group B (oral Bilastine) for blockage, discharge, itching, and sneezing. A statistically significant decrease from baseline was observed in TSS ($p < 0.0001$), NSS, and NNSS at 30 days post-once daily dosing. The findings of the current study in Indian patients are consistent with several efficacy and safety studies on intra nasal fluticasone furoate spray in other populations. In a study by Maspero JF [13], FFNS significantly improved daily mean reflective, A.M. predose instantaneous, and daily A.M. and P.M. reflective scores for nasal itching, sneezing, congestion, rhinorrhea, and ocular itching/burning, tearing/watering, and redness, compared with placebo ($p < 0.001$ for all versus placebo). In a study by Rodrigo GJ [18], Intranasal FF showed a consistent ocular and nasal efficacy along with improvement in QoL in AR patients. This review provides significant evidence that treatment with FF nasal spray at a dose of 110 mcg once daily is effective in relieving ocular and nasal symptoms in adolescents and adults with AR. In a study by Juvekar Meenesh [22], the fixed-dose combination of once-daily fluticasone furoate and oxymetazoline hydrochloride nasal spray 27.5/50 mcg was effective in relieving the nasal congestion and reduction of TNSS, TOSS and TSS in patients suffering from AR. In a study of Baroody et al [23], they determined no significant difference of quality of life and peak flow with fluticasone furoate compare to xylometazoline.

In another study by Jacobs R [25], FFNS 110 microg once daily demonstrated efficacy in relieving both the nasal and ocular symptoms of SAR in adult and adolescent patients. Similarly, In one another study by Han D [26], FFNS showed numerically better treatment effect in reducing daily TOSS than placebo (treatment difference of -0.646; $p = 0.0853$) in patients with severe ocular symptoms. FFNS 110 micrograms o.p.d. was significantly more effective than placebo in improving nasal symptoms in Chinese patients with IAR and PAR. In one another study by J. Russel May Pharm D [27], INCS have been proven to be superior to other oral anti-histamines, with a significant reduction in AR symptoms and a favourable safety profile. Study concluded, Antihistamines can be recommended for patients who experience mild, intermittent AR for symptom relief. In another study by Scadding GK [28],

FFNS consistently and significantly improved the nasal and ocular symptoms of SAR in patients sensitised to several different seasonal allergens (grass, ragweed and mountain cedar pollen) in all trials. An integrated analysis of the results also confirmed improvements in both nasal and ocular symptom scores in previously under-represented adolescent patients treated with FFNS. Similarly In study by Wu W [29], Over 4 weeks of treatment, FFNS significantly improved rTNSS, iTNSS, and the reflective scores for each individual symptom compared with placebo. In the current study, no significant safety concerns was observed in group B (Bilastine 20 mg once daily). These findings are consistent with a previous study confirming that Bilastine was safe and well-tolerated even after 1 year of treatment and was recommended as one of the preferred prescriptions for allergic rhinitis. [31,32] It was observed, patients had not reported sedation with the use of Bilastine 20 mg once daily.

Compared with first-generation OAHs that have been associated with significant adverse effects negatively impacted patients' QoL such as sedation, the use of second-generation antihistamines like bilastine, have facilitated circumvention of first-generation OAHs. [31] The limitation of our study is that data being retrospective, prone to bias and missing information and no real world evidence to substantiate the findings.

Conclusion

For the treatment of seasonal allergic rhinitis, FF NS is superior to Bilastine. Owing to single daily dose of fluticasone furoate, Patient adherence to medication may improve and thereby improvement in quality of life and further leading to reduced health care cost burden upon patients.

References

1. Yang Q, Wanq F, Li B, Wu W, Xie D, He L, Xiang N, Dong Y. The efficacy and safety of ciclesonide for the treatment of perennial allergic rhinitis: a systemic review and meta-analysis. *Braz J Otorhinolaryngol* 2018; S1808 (18)30576-7.
2. Wallace DV, Dykewicz MS, Bernstein DI, et al. The diagnosis and management of rhinitis: an updated practice parameter. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2008; 122:S1.
3. Wiksten J, Toppila-Salmi S, Makela M. Primary prevention of airway allergy. *Curr Treat Options Allergy* 2018; 5:347-55.
4. Sansila K, Eiamprapai P, Sawangjit R. Effects of self-prepared hypertonic nasal saline irrigation in allergic rhinitis: A randomized controlled trial. *Asian Pac J Allergy Immunol* 2018; 10: 12932.
5. Bui TT, Piao CH, Hyeon E, Fan Y, Van NT, Jung SY et al. The protective role of piper

- nigrum fruit extract in an ovalbumin-induced allergic rhinitis by targeting of NFκBp65 and STAT3 signalings. *Biomed Pharmacother* 2019; 109:1915-23.
6. Terada T, Kawata R. early intervention is important to prevent sensitization to new allergens. *Med Sci (Basel)* 2018; 6:E114
 7. Ellis AK, Zhu Y, Steacy LM, Walker T, Day JH. A four-way, double-blind, randomized, placebo controlled study to determine the efficacy and speed of azelastine nasal spray, versus loratadine, and cetirizine in adult subjects with allergen-induced seasonal allergic rhinitis. *Allergy Asthma Clin Immunol* 2013; 9:16.
 8. Varshney J, Varshney H, Dutta SK, Hazra A. Comparison of sensory attributes and immediate efficacy of intranasal ciclesonide and fluticasone propionate in allergic rhinitis: a randomized controlled trial. *Indian J Pharmacol* 2012; 44(5):550-4.
 9. Bozek A. Pharmacological Management of Allergic Rhinitis in the Elderly. *Drugs Aging*. 2017; 34:21-8.
 10. Cingi C, Oghan F, Eskiizmir G, Yaz A, Ural A, Erdogmus N. Desloratadine-montelukast combination improves quality of life and decreases nasal obstruction in patients with perennial allergic rhinitis. *Int Forum Allergy Rhinol*. 2013; 3:801-6.
 11. Ansari MA, Ansari NA, Montelukast versus nigella sativa for management of seasonal allergic rhinitis: a single blind comparative clinical trial. *Pak J Med Sci* 2010; 26: 249-54.
 12. Maspero JF, Walters RD, Wu W, Philpot EE, Naclerio RM, Fokkens WJ. An integrated analysis of the efficacy of fluticasone furoate nasal spray on individual nasal and ocular symptoms of seasonal allergic rhinitis. *Allergy Asthma Proc*. 2010 Nov-Dec; 31(6):483-92
 13. Abdulrahman H, Hadi U, Tarraf H, et al. Nasal allergies in the Middle Eastern population: results from the "Allergies in Middle East Survey". *Am J Rhinol Allergy* 2012; 26 Suppl 1:S3.
 14. Kabir ML, Rahman F, Hassan MQ, et al. Asthma, atopic eczema and allergic rhinoconjunctivitis in school children. *Mymensingh Med J* 2005; 14:41.
 15. Mallol J, Crane J, von Mutius E, et al. The International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC) Phase Three: A global synthesis. *Allergol Immunopathol (Madr)* 2013; 41:73.
 16. Sly RM. Changing prevalence of allergic rhinitis and asthma. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol* 1999; 82:233.
 17. Rodrigo GJ, Neffen H. Efficacy of fluticasone furoate nasal spray vs. placebo for the treatment of ocular and nasal symptoms of allergic rhinitis: a systematic review. *Clin Exp Allergy*. 2011 Feb; 41(2):160-70
 18. Torrance GW. Preferences for health outcomes and cost-utility analysis. *Am J Manag Care* 1997; 3 Suppl: S8.
 19. Soni A. Allergic rhinitis: trends in use and expenditures, 2000 to 2005. *Statistical Brief #204*, Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality; Bethesda, MD 2008.
 20. Ahmed F, Yousaf F, Asif S, Prevalence of allergic disease and related allergens in pakistan in 2007: *J Postgrad Med Inst* 2011; 25(1):14-23
 21. Juvekar Meenesh. A Real-World Observational Study to Evaluate the Safety and Effectiveness of Fluticasone Furoate-Oxymetazoline Fixed Dose Combination Nasal Spray in Patients with Allergic Rhinitis. *Clin Drug Investig*. 2024 Feb; 44(2): 123
 22. Baroody FM, Brown D, Gavanescu L, et al. Oxymetazoline adds to the effectiveness of fluticasone furoate in the treatment of perennial allergic rhinitis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2011; 127:927.
 23. Liu G, Zhou X, Chen J, Liu F. Oral antihistamines alone vs in combination with leukotriene receptor antagonists for allergic rhinitis: A Meta-analysis. *Otolaryngo Head Neck Surg*. 2018; 158:450-8
 24. Jacobs R, Martin B, Hampel F, Toler W, Ellsworth A, Philpot E. Effectiveness of fluticasone furoate 110 microg once daily in the treatment of nasal and ocular symptoms of seasonal allergic rhinitis in adults and adolescents sensitized to mountain cedar pollen. *Curr Med Res Opin*. 2009 Jun; 25(6):1393- 401
 25. Han D, Liu S, Zhang Y, Wang J, Wang D, Kong W, Wang S, Cheng L, Zhang L; Chinese Allergic Rhinitis Collaborative Research Group. Efficacy and safety of fluticasone furoate nasal spray in Chinese adult and adolescent subjects with intermittent or persistent allergic rhinitis. *Allergy Asthma Proc*. 2011 Nov-Dec; 32(6):472-81
 26. JM Russell, WK Dolen. Management of Allergic Rhinitis: A Review for the Community Pharmacist .2017; 39(12) : 2410-2419
 27. Scadding GK, Keith PK. Fluticasone furoate nasal spray consistently and significantly improves both the nasal and ocular symptoms of seasonal allergic rhinitis: a review of the clinical data. *Expert Opin Pharmacother*. 2008 Oct; 9(15):2707-15
 28. Wu W, Walters RD, Nadeau GA, Botnick W, Broughton N. An integrated analysis of the efficacy of fluticasone furoate nasal spray versus placebo on the nasal symptoms of perennial allergic rhinitis. *Allergy Asthma Proc*. 2013 May-Jun; 34(3):283-91

29. Bhargava et al, Padmanabhan K, Ramappa C. Evaluation of efficacy and safety of bilastine 20 mg tablets in adult patients with allergic rhinitis. *Int J Res Med Sci* , 10(12), 2769–2775
30. Bousquet J, Ansotegui I, Canonica GW, Zuberbier T, Baena-Cagnani CE, Bachert C et al. Establishing the place in therapy of bilastine in the treatment of allergic rhinitis according to ARIA: evidence review. *Curr Med Res Opin.* 2012; 28:131-9
31. Sastre J, Mullol J, Valero A, Valiente R. Bilastine Study Group. Efficacy and safety of bilastine 20 mg compared with cetirizine 10 mg and placebo in the treatment of perennial allergic rhinitis. *Curr Med Res Opin.* 2012; 28:121-30.
32. Lynde CW, Sussman G, Dion PL, Guenther L, Hébert J, Rao J et al. Multidisciplinary real-world experience with bilastine, a second-generation antihistamine. *J. Drugs Dermatol.* 2020; 19:145-54.